

IHDEA 2025 Decadal Session Summary

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Summary

The Decadal Session was a purposefully interactive session, involving the use of Miro boards and small and large group discussions. The three concepts that rose to the top were:

1. A new longer-term funding structure designed to enhance collaboration, reuse, and maintenance of software;
2. The purposeful development of interoperable mission tools through cross-institutional development; and
3. Increased collaboration with efforts in other sciences through involvement in their conferences covering standards and archiving efforts.

The first topic is one that has been highly prioritized by the software community in recent years (e.g., Ringuette et al. 2024¹). However, the topic was skipped due to the U.S. government shutdown and the resulting funders not in attendance.

Topic 2 drew the most discussion. There was general agreement that a slightly higher level of funding will be needed due to challenges of collaborating across institutions and the extra work to increase reusability of mission software. However, there was also palpable optimism that this slight increase of funding would more than pay off once a few foundational softwares were created from currently existing options. Then, the community could shift to contributing to existing tools to increase applicability to new missions or provide high quality justifications why a new tool would be needed.

Topic 3 can be succinctly summarized by a paraphrase of a participant's comment, 'Look at what others are doing!' There was strong interest to collaborate with related fields such as Earth Science, Astrophysics, and Planetary Science to develop and shift standards in Heliophysics to take advantage of where standards in other fields have demonstrated benefit (e.g., by attending the ESIP² workshop). Similar collaboration was also desired across data repositories, both internationally in Heliophysics and in related sciences, to accelerate progress in resolving shared problems. This could be through a yearly workshop focused on data repositories and services where the international Heliophysics data archiving community shares their challenges and recently solved problems. However, a wider cross-science connection on those same problems was also desired, potentially through an existing or future relevant group in the Research Data Alliance (e.g., the Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences Data Community of Practice³) and participation in the related workshops.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14047903>

² Earth Science Information Partners, <https://www.esipfed.org/>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/earth-space-and-environmental-sciences-data>

Session Notes

This session began with a short presentation introducing the audience to the Decadal Survey, why it is important, and the structure of the session (Thomas et al. 2025⁴). After an icebreaker exercise, the audience actively participated in ideation using a Miro board on potential tasks and collaborations in support of the Decadal Survey (<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjvJ94KlcU=/>). Everyone then voted with colored dots on their favorite ideas with a limit of three votes per person (Figures 1 and 2 below). Some used emoji reactions instead of dots; both were counted equally.

Instructions given on the Miro board:

This Decadal Survey session uses the US Solar and Space Physics Decadal Survey as a starting point to discuss what international data environment is needed to advance our research infrastructure. <https://doi.org/10.17226/27938>

Decadal Survey Challenges of Interest:

1. “Foster Research with Combined Ground and Space Data”
2. “Foster the HelioSystems Laboratory (HSL)”
3. “Foster Archive Research”

What improvements are needed to make these challenges easier?

Figure 1: Left half of the idea portion of the Miro board.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17488694>

Figure 2: Right half of the idea portion of the Miro board.

The ideas with at least 5 votes or positive reactions were:

1. **(16 votes)** 5,6,7-year grants instead of 1-3 to allow for deep research without the distraction of grant writing.
2. (9 votes) Collaborate across different fields of space archives in sharing common problems not just associated w/ Helio data.
3. **(8 votes)** MORE funding.
4. (8 votes) shared ground and space data standards.
5. **(6 votes)** fund generic mission tools by paying 2 missions to create and use the same generic tools, plus a 3rd institution to participate and help make the code more generic.
6. (6 votes) Come up with a way to make publishing open source software less bureaucratic for large space agencies.
7. **(5 votes)** fund software maintenance.
8. (5 votes) Look at what Earth data systems are doing!!
9. **(5 votes)** Grants to restore legacy data.
10. (5 votes) Improve traceability of following archive standards to real scientific results to highlight impact that best archiving practices has.

Of these ideas, several tended to focus on funding (**bold**). However, there was general agreement that not much could be done by those in attendance, so those topics were avoided in the group discussions.

The audience separated into three groups and selected three topics per group, ignoring those directly dealing with funding, and focused their discussions on those selected topics with the following three questions:

1. How do we work together?
2. What projects can we structure now to collaborate on?
3. Who is concerned, what work is already in progress, how to combine efforts?

Notes from those discussions are shown in Figures 3-5 below. Groups 1 and 2 both discussed item 5 at length, group 2 additionally discussed item 10 and cloud computing, and group 3 worked on items 2 and 8.

After these separate discussions, the groups combined for a wider discussion. Notes from that discussion are shown in Figure 6. A substantial portion of the discussion focused on item 5, working towards multi-mission shared tools. There was general agreement that a slightly higher level of funding will be needed due to challenges of collaborating across institutions and the extra work to increase reusability of mission software. However, there was also palpable optimism that this slight increase of funding would more than pay off once a few foundational softwares were created from currently existing options. Then, the community could shift to contributing to existing tools to increase applicability to new missions or provide high quality justifications why a new tool would be needed.

There was also high interest in increasing collaboration with other related sciences, but time did not allow for further discussion.

Figure 3: Notes from Group 1's discussions. The topics selected for the discussion are shown in orange.

Figure 4: Notes from Group 2's discussions. The topics selected for the discussion are shown in orange.

Figure 5: Notes from Group 3's discussions. The topics selected for the discussion are shown in orange (top center). Connections between topics are shown with thin arrows.

Figure 6: Notes from the larger group's discussion at the end of the session. Potential working group topics shown in green.